

Feasibility Studies on the Preparation of Bioethanol from Taro Roots

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Abstract

In this research, taro roots were used as a source for preparation of bioethanol by enzymatic hydrolysis followed by fermentation. In enzymatic hydrolysis, termamyl (α -amylase) was used for liquefaction and saczyme (glucoamylase) for saccharification. The substrate concentration, enzyme volume used and liquefaction time were investigated for maximum yield of fermentable sugar in liquefaction step. The maximum fermentable sugars of 185 mg/g have obtained by liquefaction using 250 mg/L substrate concentration, 4 mL of termamyl and 3 h of liquefaction time. In saccharification step, effects of enzyme and saccharification time on the yield of fermentable sugar were also studied. The fermentable sugar obtained in enzymatic hydrolysis was determined by Lane and Eynon method. The maximum fermentable sugar of 722 mg/g was obtained when saccharification was carried out with 9 mL of saczyme for saccharification time of 10 h at 60 °C and pH 4.3. The fermentable sugar from enzymatic hydrolysis was fermented by using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. In the fermentation process, concentration of fermentable sugar, fermentation time, fermentation temperature and yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) content were studied for the maximum strength of bioethanol. After fermentation, the ethanol content in broth was determined by alcohol meter and the maximum strength, 10 % (v/v) was obtained under the conditions of 2.4 % (w/w) yeast content, 200 g/L of substrate concentration (sugar), 35°C of fermentation temperature and 4 day-course of fermentation time. After fractional distillation, the ethanol strength was determined by gas chromatography (GC). In addition, total acidity, pH, refractive index and chloride content and specific gravity of bioethanol were determined.

Key words: Taro roots, liquefaction, saccharification, fermentation

Introduction

Bioethanol refers to ethyl alcohol produced by microbial fermentation process, as opposed to synthetically produced ethanol from petrochemical sources. The most cost effective way to produce commercial ethyl alcohol is by the hydration of petroleum-derived ethylene. As petroleum becomes scarce and more expensive, fermentation of simple sugars by microorganism is extensively used to produce ethanol from renewable sugar-containing biomass such as sugary materials, starchy materials and lignocellulosic materials derived from agricultural residues and wood residues. When ethanol is produced by fermentation of sugar feedstock such as sugar cane, molasses, sugar beet and sweet sorghum by using yeast specifically *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, yeast can directly consume simple sugars and convert them to ethanol. However, starch and cellulose feedstock are a polymer of glucose and cannot be fermented directly by yeast. They have to be converted or depolymerized to glucose prior to fermentation. Depolymerization or hydrolysis of starch is much simpler and more cost effective than that of cellulosic materials and can be achieved by acid or enzyme or a combination of both (Chandel et al., 2014).

The starch hydrolysis by enzymes is a two-stage process involving liquefaction and saccharification. Liquefaction is a step in which starch is degraded by an endo-acting enzyme namely, α -amylase, which hydrolyzes only α -1,4 glucose units causing dramatically drop in viscosity of gelatinized starch. The dextrans that obtained after liquefaction, is further hydrolyzed ultimately to glucose by glucoamylase enzyme which can hydrolyze both α -1,4 and α -1,6 glycosidic linkages (Fisher, 2004). Glucose is then converted to ethanol by yeast. At the end of fermentation, approximately 10% (v/v) ethanol is obtained, depending on solid loading during fermentation. It is subjected to distillation and dehydration to remove water (Schwaiger et al., 2011).

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Materials and Methods

Materials

Fresh taro roots in medium size were purchased from Taunggyi District, Shan State. Hydrochloric acid (sp gr = 1.18) and sulphuric acid (sp gr = 1.84) (BDH, Analar grade) were purchased from Kemiko Chemical dealer, Pabeden Township, Yangon Region. Termamyl (approximate density = 1.6 g/ml) and Saczyme (approximate density = 1.15 g/ml) (Novozyme, Denmark) were purchased from MY Associates Co., Ltd., Sanchaung Township, Yangon Region.

Preparation of Taro Roots

Fresh taro roots were washed with running water and allowed to dry at room temperature for about 1 h. The outer skin was peeled off and sliced into small pieces which were then dried at 60°C in a hot air oven for about 5 h. The dried chips were then ground into fine powder and sieved through an 80 mesh stainless steel screen. The samples were stored in the airtight bottles.

Determination of Moisture Content in Taro Root Powder

The moisture content of taro root powder was determined by oven drying method (AOAC934.01).

Determination of Ash Content

The ash content of each sample was determined according to AOAC930.05.

Determination of Starch Content

Taro root powder, 5 g was placed in a conical flask to which 100 mL of distilled water and 20 mL of 25 % (% v/v) hydrochloric acid was added. The mixture was then boiled gently by using a thermostatically controlled water bath for 150 min. After dissolving, the solution was cooled down and neutralized with 30 % (% w/v) sodium hydroxide solution. Then, the solution was filtered and diluted to 500 mL with distilled water and the amount of reducing sugar was determined titrationally by using Lane-Eynon Method. The starch content was obtained by multiplying the sugar content with factor 0.93. The whole procedure was repeated three times. The yield percent of starch was calculated and the results are shown in Table 1.

$$\text{Reducing sugar content (\%)} = \frac{\text{factor} \times Y \times 100}{\text{titre} \times W}$$

$$\text{Starch content (\%)} = \text{reducing sugar content (\%)} \times 0.93$$

Where,

- Y = Total volume of sugar solution (g)
- titre = Titrate volume of sugar solution (ml)
- W = Weight of sample (g)

Enzymatic Hydrolysis of Taro Roots

Taro root powder, 250 g was mixed with 1 L of water in a beaker and heated at 70°C for 30 min. The gelatinized slurry was maintained at pH 6.9 by using phosphate buffer solutions (pH 6.9). The slurry was mixed with 4 mL of termamyl enzyme and liquefied at 85°C for 3 h with continuous stirring. The thin syrup obtained from liquefaction was immediately cooled down to 60°C and pH was adjusted to reach 4.3 by adding hydrochloric acid and maintained at pH 4.3 by using acetate buffer solution (pH 4.3). Saczyme, 9 mL was then added and stirred occasionally for 10 h. The temperature was maintained at 60°C throughout the

saccharification process. After saccharification, the syrup was heated to 100 °C to denature the enzyme.

During liquefaction, the effect of different substrate concentration (150 g/L, 200 g/L, 250 g/L, 300 g /L), volume of termamyl (1 mL, 2 mL, 3 mL, 4 mL, 5 mL), and liquefaction time (90 min, 120 min, 150 min, 180 min, 210 min) on the yield of fermentable sugar were observed. Saccharification of liquefied slurry was performed by varying the volume of saczym (enzyme) used (7 mL, 8 mL, 9 ml, 10 mL) and saccharification time (4 h, 6 h, 8 h, 10 h, 12 h).

Fermentation of Sugar obtained from Hydrolysis of Taro Stems

For fermentation, the yeast, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was cultured in the fermentable sugar solution in a stainless steel Makeshift fermenter as shown in Figure 5. The solution was stirred thoroughly so that the yeast was uniformly dispersed in sugar solution. Fermentation was carried out at 35 °C at pH 4.3 under anaerobic condition.

In fermentation process, varying the fermentable sugar concentration (150 g/L, 200 g/L, 250 g/L, 300 g/L), fermentation time (1 day, 2 days, 3 days, 4 days, 5 days), fermentation temperature (25°C, 30°C, 35°C, 40°C, 45°C) and yeast content (1.2 %, 1.6%, 2.0 %, 2.4 %, 2.8 % w/w) were conducted to obtain the maximum strength of ethanol.

Ethanol was then separated from the fermented broth by distillation and further purified by fractional distillation using fractionating column (105 cm in length, 2 cm in outside diameter, 1.75 in inside diameter) as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 1. Taro Roots

Figure. 2 Slices of Taro Roots

Figure 3. Taro Root Powder

Figure 4. Enzymatic Hydrolysis of Taro Root Powder

Figure 5. Makeshift Fermenter for fermentation

Figure 6. Separation of ethanol by fractional distillation

Determination of Fermentable Sugar by Lane and Eynon Method

Fehling's solution, 10 mL was added into a 250 mL conical flask and 10 mL of sugar solution was added into the Fehling solution. The mixture was then boiled and 1 mL of sugar solution was added at a time during boiling until the color of the solution changed from blue to red. A few drops of methylene blue indicator were added and titration continued until the color turned red. The reducing sugar content was calculated (Pearson, 1976).

Determination of Ethanol Strength by Gas Chromatography (GC)

Ethanol strength was also determined by gas chromatography by using GC 2010 SHIMADZU equipped with flame ionization detector (FID). The sample was taken and gathered into a syringe and then injected into an ejector port on the device. The temperature of the injector port must be in excess of the boiling point for the sample to obtain accurate readings. This allowed ethanol to convert into gas, which was then pushed into the filters by nitrogen carrier gas. As the gases were passed through the filters, the compounds were identified by electronic detector and the alcohol content was then determined.

Analysis of Physicochemical Properties of Bioethanol

Determination of Refractive Index

The refractive index of the bioethanol was measured by refractometer (Shibuya Optical Co., Ltd, Tokyo, Japan). The measurement was carried out at 20°C. The results are shown in Table 5.

Determination of pH

The pH of prepared sample was determined by using a digital pH meter (pH300, HANNA). The glass electrode assembly was first calibrated by using buffer solutions of pH 7 and the electrode was adjusted to those values. After that, pH of the sample was measured and the results are shown in Table 5.

Determination of Total Acidity

A 10 mL bioethanol was put in a conical flask with a pipette and two drops of phenolphthalein was then added. It was titrated with 0.1 N sodium hydroxide solution from a burette until the end point was reached. The above procedure was carried out in triplicate. The percent acidity was calculated and the results are shown in Table 5.

$$\text{Total acidity as acetic acid (\%)} = \frac{\text{titre} \times \text{normality of NaOH} \times 0.06 \times 100}{\text{volume of sample taken}}$$

Determination of Chloride Content

Chloride content was determined by using MI 414 chloride meter (Martini Instrument, Romania). One of two cuvetts was filled with 10 mL of distilled water and other cuvette was filled with 10 mL of sample. Chloride reagent 1.5 mL was added to each cuvette, recovered the caps and swirl gently for 30 s. Then the caps were removed from each cuvette and 0.5 mL of chloride reagent 2 to each cuvette was added. Then, the cuvette was swirled gently for 30 s. The cuvette with distilled water was placed into the holder and calibrated to display to show 0.0. After calibration, the cuvette with distilled water was removed and the cuvette with the sample was inserted securely into the holder and the concentration of chloride in the sample was read and the results are shown in Table 5.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the starch content, moisture content and ash content of taro roots. It can be seen in this table that taro root contained 79.26 % of starch. The starch content related to the yield of sugars, namely, glucose because of its formulation of large glucose units joined together by glucosidic bonds.

Enzymatic Hydrolysis of taro root powder was carried out by using termamyl enzyme (α -amylase) and saczyme enzyme (glucoamylase) for liquefaction and saccharification respectively. Liquefaction of taro root powder was performed by using termamyl at 85°C and pH 6.9. Termamyl can hydrolyze α -1,4 bonds at random points in the starch molecules and produce a type of sugar called dextrose and as a result, the viscosity of gelatinized starch solutions has reduced (Kearsly, 1995). This enzyme cannot, however, hydrolyze α -1,6 bonds in amylopectin.

Figure 7 represents the effect of substrate concentration on the yield of fermentable sugar with various enzyme dosages. Fermentable sugar yield increased with increased in substrate concentration from 150 g/L to 250 g/L and at the substrate concentration 250 g/L, the fermentable sugar became 185 mg/g. Further increasing in the substrate concentration beyond 250 g/L caused decreasing of the yield of fermentable sugar. Similar observations have been reported by Kolusheva, (2006) who has worked with high starchy powder concentration (250 g/L). The activity of enzyme related to the viscosity of the substrate solution and viscosity can affect the substrate–enzyme interaction and thus reduced the amount of fermentable sugar (Aderbigbe, 2013). The yield of fermentable sugar also increased with increase in volume of enzyme termamyl. At enzyme volumes, 4 mL and 5 mL, the yield of fermentable sugar were the same (185 mg/g). The enzyme dosage of 6 ml affected the yield of fermentable sugar and decreased to 180 mg/g.

Figure 8 also shows the effect of liquefaction time on the yield of fermentable sugar. The maximum yield of fermentable sugar, 185 mg/g was obtained at the liquefaction time of 3 h. The maximum yield of fermentable sugar, 185 mg/g was obtained with the enzyme dosage of 4 mL and liquefaction time of 180 min. Jacques (2003) stated that the overdose or prolong treatment in liquefaction step can lead to the formation of maltulose (4- α -D-glucopyranosyl-D-fructose), which is resistant to hydrolysis by α -amylases and glucoamylases.

Saccharification of liquefied taro root powder was continuously performed by using saczyme at 60°C and pH 4.3. Saczyme can hydrolyze α -1,4 linkages as well as α -1,6 linkages in the liquefied starch (amylose and amylopectin) (Kearsley, 1995).

Figure 9 shows the effect of volume of saczyme and saccharification time on the yield of fermentable sugar with various saccharification time. The maximum fermentable sugar 722.8 mg/g was achieved when saccharification was carried out with 9 mL of saczyme for saccharification time of 10 h, where the dextrose equivalent was 91.16 at the end of saccharification. Aderbigbe (2013) stated that at the end of saccharification process, the dextrose equivalent is >70 . The yield of fermentable sugar did not increase although the enzyme volume was increased to 10 mL with saccharification time, 12 h. It was possible that increase in fermentable sugar concentration inhibited the enzyme activity on starch hydrolysis.

Fermentable sugar from taro root powder was fermented by inoculating the yeast, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* at pH 4.3. As shown in Table 2, fermentable sugar, 200 g/L was the suitable concentration to obtain the maximum strength, 10 % (v/v) of ethanol. This was due to the presence of product (ethanol) inhibition. According to Kumar (1998), the strength of ethanol can limit the growth of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* due to its tolerance only about 10-13 % ethanol.

From Figure 10 with the yeast content, 1.6 % and 2.0 % (w/w), fermentation has not been completed after 4 days of fermentation but fermentation with yeast content, 2.4 % and 2.8 % gave the maximum yield of 10 % (v/v) ethanol at the end of fermentation course of 4 days. This fact showed that the yeast content did not affect the alcohol yield. The yeast content, however, affected the time taken for the fermentation to be completed. It can also be seen in Table 3 that fermentation temperature was related to the growth of yeast and its metabolic activity to be able to produce ethanol. When the fermentation temperature reached to 35°C, the highest yield of ethanol (10 % v/v) was obtained. The increasing temperature more than 35°C can cause reduction in the yield of ethanol. It may be mainly due to the denaturing of the yeast cells. Based on the yield of ethanol, the most suitable temperature was 35°C. It can also be seen in Table 4 that yeast growth increased gradually up to 4 days of inoculation time but the growth of yeast ceased after 4 days. This was due to inhibitory effect of ethanol formed during fermentation on cell growth (Kumar, 1998). Overall, the maximum yield of ethanol has been achieved under the conditions of 2.4 % (w/w) yeast content, 200 g/L of substrate concentration (sugar), 35°C of fermentation temperature and 4 day-course of fermentation time.

In order to increase the strength of bioethanol, fractional distillation was conducted using fractionating column (105 cm height, 2 cm outside diameter, 1.75 cm inside diameter). After 4 h fractionating time, the separated ethanol was analyzed by gas chromatography (GC). The chromatogram for bioethanol is shown in APPENDIX B. According to the results of GC analysis, the ethanol strength was 81.482 % v/v (reflux ratio = 1.1). Some physicochemical properties of bioethanol such as specific gravity, refractive index, chloride content, pH and total acidity (as acetic acid) are shown in Table 5. Total acidity, pH, refractive index and chloride content of bioethanol from are 0.004 %, 6.5, 1.36 and 0.1 mg/L respectively. These values except ethanol strength were in agreement with the Asian Ethanol Philippines National Standard Specification for Anhydrous Undenatured bioethanol Fuel shown in Table 5 (global biofuel, 2014). Specific gravities of bioethanol, 0.8665 was very close to the specific gravity of absolute ethanol, 0.789.

Table 1. Composition of Taro Root Powder

	Components	Composition (% w/w)
1	Moisture content	10.04
2	Ash content	3.25
3	Starch content	79.26

Figure 7. Effect of termamyl enzyme on the yield of fermentable sugar in the liquefaction of taro root powder

Figure 8. Effect of liquefaction time on the yield of fermentable sugar in the liquefaction of taro root powder

Figure 9. Effect of saccharification time on the yield of fermentable sugar in the saccharification of liquefied taro root powder

Table 2. Effect of Fermentable Sugar Concentration on the Strength of Ethanol

No.	Substrate concentration (g/L)	Yeast content (% w/w)	Fermentation time (day)	pH	Fermentation temperature (°C)	Ethanol Strength (% v/v)
1	50	2.4	4	4.3	35	3
2	100	2.4	4	4.3	35	5.5
3	150	2.4	4	4.3	35	8.5
4	200	2.4	4	4.3	35	10
5	250	2.4	4	4.3	35	9
6	300	2.4	4	4.3	35	8.5

Table 3. Effect of Fermentation Temperature on the Strength of Ethanol

No.	Substrate concentration (g/L)	Yeast content (% w/w)	Fermentation time (day)	pH	Fermentation temperature (°C)	Ethanol Strength (% v/v)
1	200	2.4	4	4.3	25	6.5
2	200	2.4	4	4.3	30	8
3	200	2.4	4	4.3	35	10
4	200	2.4	4	4.3	40	7.5
5	200	2.4	4	4.3	45	7
6	200	2.4	4	4.3	25	6.5

Table 4. Effect of Fermentation Time on the Strength of Ethanol

Source	Substrate concentration (g/L)	Fermentation temperature (°C)	pH	Fermentation time (day)	Ethanol Strength (% v/v)	Yield of Ethanol (% w/w)
Taro root	200	35	4.3	1	4	30
				2	7	52
				3	9	67
				4	10	75
				5	10	75

Table 5. Physicochemical Properties of Bioethanol after Fractional Distillation

No.	Properties	Ethanol (Taro root)	Literature Value* (Anhydrous Ethanol)
1	Ethanol strength** (% v/v)	81.482	99.3 (min.)
2	pH	6.5	6.5-9
3	Specific gravity	0.8566	0.789
4	Total acidity (% mass) (as acetic acid)	0.004	0.007
5	Refractive index	1.36	1.36
6	Chloride content (mg/L)	0.1	40 (max.)
7	Appearance	Clear and visibly free of suspended matter	Clear and colourless

* Source of data: global biofuel, 2014

** These characteristics were determined at the laboratory of Australasia Marketing Trade & Technology Co., Ltd (Amtt Co., Ltd), Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.
The experiments for other characteristics were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry, Dagon University.

Figure 10. Effect of yeast content on the strength of ethanol

Conclusion

In enzymatic hydrolysis of taro root powder, the highest fermentable sugars have been reached to 722 mg/g under the suitable conditions. Anaerobic fermentation of sugar was carried out by using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* followed by simple distillation and obtained the ethanol contents of 10% (v/v). Based on the results of GC analysis, the strength of ethanol enhanced to 81.44 after fractional distillation. Total acidity, pH, refractive index and chloride content of bioethanol were 0.004 % (mass), 6.5, 1.36 and 0.1 mg/L respectively. The specific gravity of ethanol was 0.8566 and is much close to that of anhydrous ethanol, 0.789. These physicochemical properties except strength of ethanol are in agreement with Asian Ethanol Philippines National Standard Specification for Anhydrous Undenatured bioethanol Fuel (global biofuel, 2014). Based on these processes, anhydrous bioethanol may produce using cheap raw materials and sources by optimizing certain parameters in proceeding dehydration of resulting bioethanol.

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Cost Estimation for Production of Ethanol from Taro Roots by Enzymatic Hydrolysis followed by Fermentation

Basis: 500 Liters of Ethanol per batch (one batch required 4 days)

Operation Days = 280 days per year

No.	Particular	Amount	Total Quality	Unit Cost (Kyats)	Total Cost (Kyats)
I	Material Cost				
(i)	Taro Root	1389 kg / batch	1389 x 70	900 k / kg	87,507,000
(ii)	Termamyl	22 L / batch	22 x 70	2500 k / L	3,850,000
(iii)	Saczyme	50 kg / batch	50 x 70	2500 k / L	8,750,000
(iv)	Water	5555 L / batch	5555 x 70	10 k / L	3,888,500
(v)	Yeast	24 kg / batch	24 x 70	1500 k / kg	2,520,000
II	Labour Cost			5000	
(i)	Supervisor	1 person		k/person/day	1,400,000
(ii)	Unskilled Labour	2 person		2500 k/person/day	1,400,000
III	Utility Cost				
(i)	Electricity	400 units / batch	400 x 70	75 k / unit	2,100,000
(ii)	Water	1000L / batch	1000 x 70	10 k / L	700,000
Direct Production Cost					107,075,500

Assume that Purchased equipment cost, P = 3000000 k

Salvage value, L = 10000 k

Service life, n = 15 y

$$\frac{P - L}{n}$$

$$\frac{3000000 - 10000}{15} = 199333 \text{ k}$$

$$\frac{107075500 + 199333}{35000} = 3064 \text{ k}$$

Note: Only raw materials, labour, utility and packaging costs were taken into consideration in direct production cost.

Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.